

Nutrient Concentration via Electrodialysis from AnMBR effluent for Subsequent Recovery: Energy Consumption and System Performance Optimization

S. Hernández-Cuenca*, J. Serralta*, R. Barat*, J. Carrillo-Abad** and A. Bouzas**

* CALAGUA – Unitat Mixta UV-UPV, Institut Universitari d'Investigació d'Enginyeria de l'Aigua i Medi Ambient – IIAMA, Universitat Politècnica de Valencia, Camí de Vera s/n, 46022 Valencia, Spain
(E-mail: silhercu@etsii.upv.es; jserralt@hma.upv.es; rababa@dihma.upv.es)

** CALAGUA – Unitat Mixta UV-UPV, Departament d'Enginyeria Química, Universitat de València,AVINGUDA de la Universitat s/n, 46100 Burjassot, Valencia, Spain
(E-mail: jordi.carrillo@uv.es; alberto.bouzas@uv.es)

Abstract

This study assesses different operating modes of a bench-scale electrodialysis (ED) plant for nutrient concentration from an aerated Anaerobic Membrane Bioreactor (AnMBR) effluent. Long-term and short-term ED tests were conducted to optimize system performance with two aims: generate a concentrated stream with a high nutrient content, and produce high-quality reclaimed water. Operational modes in one stage and two-stages, total membrane area, working/relaxation periods and influent nutrient concentrations were evaluated. Results showed a better ED system performance operating in two-stages, with 30 cell pairs and with higher influent nutrient concentrations. Concentrations up to 1005 mgNH₄-N/L and 117 mgPO₄-P /L in the concentrated stream and low to 3.5 mgNH₄-N/L and 0.7 mgPO₄-P /L in the diluted stream were achieved in long-term tests.

Keywords

AnMBR; circular economy; electrodialysis; energy consumption; nutrient recovery; water reclamation

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the growing global population has increased the demand for essential resources like water and food, which requires fertilizers rich in nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P). Urban wastewater (UWW) is a viable source for nutrient recovery but must also be treated to prevent eutrophication. Although nutrient recovery is easier in the sludge line, only a limited fraction of N and P is available, and the process can be costly due to chemical and energy requirements (Bacardí Godoy, 2021). Therefore, it is crucial to develop technologies to recover nutrients from the main line, despite its lower nutrient concentrations. The anaerobic membrane bioreactor (AnMBR) is a promising solution, as it valorises organic matter and produces effluents with significant NH₄-N and PO₄-P concentrations with low energy consumption (Godifredo et al., 2023). However, it must be integrated with post-treatment processes to achieve discharge limits and allowing nutrient recovery using technologies such as crystallization and membrane contactors. In this sense, at least concentrations of 60 and 500 mg/L of PO₄-P and NH₄-N, respectively, are advisable to be economically feasible (Robles et al., 2020).

Electrodialysis for nutrient recovery

Electrodialysis (ED) separates ions into diluted and concentrated streams using cation- and anion-selective membranes driven by electrical force. Initially applied to concentrate brackish water, its use has expanded to urban wastewater treatment, particularly for nutrient recovery. In fact, Proskynitopoulou et al. (2024), achieved nitrogen and phosphorus concentration factors of 7.9 and 1.7, respectively, but with significant energy consumption (165 kWh/kg NH₄-N and 21600 kWh/kg PO₄-P recovered). Good recovery rates, long membrane lifespans, and good selectivity are some of the main benefits of ED technology. However, its main drawback is its high energy requirements. Then, optimisation of energy consumption is necessary, selecting best operating conditions, alternating modes, and adjusting membrane area. Despite progress using ED for nutrient recovery, gaps remain in optimising system performance from real effluents, particularly in AnMBR treatments. This work aims to determine optimal ED configuration for nutrient recovery, while

producing high-quality reclaimed water compliant with the new DIRECTIVE (EU) 2024/3019 in diluted stream. Therefore, a bench-scale study was conducted to optimise ED systems for nutrient recovery from AnMBR effluents. Experiments included different operational modes (galvanostatic and potentiostatic), total membrane areas (10-30 cell pairs), relaxation/work periods and influent nutrient concentrations, focusing on energy consumption, removal efficiency, and recovery rates.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The work was performed at bench-scale. The following paragraphs summarise the experimental procedure of the ED experiments carried out.

Wastewater

Effluent from an AnMBR pilot at Conca del Carraixet WWTP (Valencia, Spain) was used, after being aerated, for all trials. AnMBR effluent is aerated to remove sulphides, preventing CaSO₄ bulk precipitation. Table 1 shows the average concentrations during the experimental period.

Table 1. AnMBR average effluent concentrations

	Normal effluent		Concentrated effluent	
	Average	SD	Average	SD
NH ₄ -N (mg/L)	52.2	7.6	72.0	6.3
PO ₄ -P (mg/L)	6.9	0.6	10.0	1.7
SO ₄ -S (mg/L)	38.9	22.6	36.5	27.6
S ₂ O ₃ -S (mg/L)	8.0	7.4	7.2	0.2
S ²⁻ (mg/L)	< 0.1	-	< 0.1	-
Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	212.5	30.8	193.5	11.0

Experimental set-up and procedure

The study used a bench-scale electro dialysis stack (64-002) from PCCell GmbH, with up to 30 cell pairs and a 5 L/h flow rate per cell pair. It featured Ti/RuO₂ electrodes, PC-SKN cation, and Acid-100-OT anion exchange membranes, with flow rates (0–100 L/h) managed by diaphragm pump valves. Conductivity, temperature, and flow were monitored, while a Voltcraf PPS-11815 power supply ensured stable current/voltage. Tanks (2 L diluted/concentrated, 5 L electrolyte) and automatic hydraulic control were PC-operated. The configuration used n-cell pairs (CEM/AEM), and 0.01 M H₂SO₄ as the electrolyte, maintaining pH below 5 to prevent precipitation. Long-term and short-term experiments were conducted to optimise ED performance. All these experiments were performed in semi-batch mode since the concentrated stream was recirculated to the feed tank until the end of the experiment, and the diluted stream was recirculated during a cycle and renewed when the cycle finished. Long-term tests included single-stage ED at 0.1A and 7.5V, as well as two-stages combining galvanostatic (0.1A) and potentiostatic (7.5V) modes. Tests with 10, 20, and 30 cell pairs (CP) assessed total membrane area impact on energy consumption, considering manufacturer limits. Short-term experiments explored working/relaxation times (10 min work/10 min relaxation) and different influent nutrient concentrations, working at 7.5V. In all cases, cycles ended at 0.15 mS/cm in diluted stream. Long-term experiments ended at 30-40 mS/cm in the concentrated stream and short-term experiments ended after four cycles. Samples from all streams were collected at the start and after each cycle.

Analytical methods

An ion chromatograph (IC) (883 Basic IC Plus, Metrohm, Switzerland) was used to analyse each sample. A pH meter (Sentix® 41, WTW) was used to measure the pH and a conductivity meter (TetraCon® 325, WTW) to measure conductivity in the concentrate, diluted, and electrolyte streams. Experiments were conducted at room temperature ($22\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Similar P and N concentrations in diluate (0.9 ± 0.2 mgP/L and 4.9 ± 1.5 mgN/L) and concentrated (88.6 ± 28.5 mgP/L and 860.8 ± 145.0 mgN/L) streams were achieved in every long-term test.

Operational mode: 0.1V, 7.5V and 0.1V+7.5V

Figure 1 shows the energy consumption obtained for each trial. Results demonstrate better performance at 7.5V compared to 0.1A, improved when combining both galvanostatic and potentiostatic mode. Recovery efficiencies of 84% and 73% and removal efficiencies of 87% and 88% for nitrogen and phosphorus, respectively, were achieved in 0.1A + 7.5V test.

Figure 1. Energy consumption per kilogram and volume of treated water at different operational modes.

Membrane area: 10 CP, 20 CP and 30 CP

Results shown in Figure 2 demonstrate that the higher the number of cell pairs the lower the energy consumption. 30 CP was the best scenario for optimising system performance. Improvement in energy consumption decreased when increasing CP. All trials seem to have similar behaviour regarding efficiencies, with values above $76.9\pm 3.1\%$ and up to 84.7% for nitrogen and phosphorus recovery and $88.6\pm 2.3\%$ and $83.4\pm 4.3\%$ for nitrogen and phosphorus removal.

Figure 2. Energy consumption per kilogram and volume of treated water for different number of cell pairs.

Working/Relaxation periods

No improvement in system performance when operating with working/relaxation periods was observed, as can be seen in Figure 3. Moreover, above $87.6\pm 9.6\%$ and $60.8\pm 1.1\%$ of nitrogen and phosphorus were recovered and $88.7\pm 0.2\%$ and $76.9\pm 3.1\%$ were removed in both tests.

Figure 3. Energy consumption per kilogram and treated volume of water for working/relaxation tests.

Wastewater nutrient concentration

Nitrogen and phosphorus concentrations in concentrated stream were higher with higher inlet concentrations (76.5 mg NH₄-N/L and 11.1 mg PO₄-P/L), thus enhancing the efficiency of subsequent recovery processes and leading to a decrease in energy consumption per kilogram recovered. In addition, energy consumption per treated water also decreased due to the higher influent salinity, as Figure 4 shows.

Figure 4. Energy consumption per kilogram and treated water for different influent concentrations.

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